

REGRESSIYON MODELNI SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA MAPLE TIZIMIDAN FOYDALANISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6413746>

MAQOLA TARIXI

Qabul qilindi: 15-mart 2022

Ma'qullandi: 20-mart 2022

Chop etildi: 25-mart 2022

KALIT SO'ZLAR

regressiya, kriteriya,
model, adekvat,
aproximatsiya,
qiymatdorlik, Maple, seq,
add, vector.

Statistik ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlashda regression taxlil bo'yicha tajriba natijalarining matematik modeli-chiziqli regressiya tenglamasini eng kichik kvadratlar usulidan foydalanib tuzish va bu modellarni sifatini, adekvatligini hamda regressiya koeffitsentlarining qiymatdorligini baholash masalalari ko'rilgan[5,8,9]. Bu masalalarni yechishda modelning sifatni baholshda o'rtacha

ASOSIY QISM. Kuzatuvlar natijasida sotiladigan maxsulotning soni y bilan uning reklamasi uchun sariflangan x miqdor

x	1.5	4.0	5.0	7.0	8.5	10.0	11.0	12.5
y	5.0	4.5	7.0	6.5	9.5	9.0	11.0	9.0

Bu bog'lanishni to'g'ri chiziqli regressiya tenglamasini aniqlash uchun

ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi vaqtda har qanday jiddiy statistik hisob-kitoblar, qoida tariqasida, kompyuterlarda va birinchi navbatda, shaxsiy kompyuterlarda amalga oshiriladi. Ushbu maqolada Maple dasturidan foydalanib muxandislik va iqtisodiyot masalalarining tajriba natijalari bo'yicha tuzilgan matematik modellarning sifat va samadorligi hamda raqamli usullardan foydalanib tahlil va qaror qabul qilishda axamiyatli ekanligi ko'rsatilgan[1,2,3,7,8,9,10,11].

xatolik aproksimatsiyasi formulasidan, modelni-regressiya tenglamasini adekvatligini Fisherning F-kriteriyasidan, regressiya koeffitsentlarining qiymatdorligini Student kriteriyasidan foydalanilgan. Bu barcha masalalarni yechishda Maple tizimidagi usullari va dasturlardan foydalanilgan [1,2,3,7,8,9,10,11].

orasidagi bog'lanishni aniqlash bo'yicha o'tkazilgan tajribalarning natijalari quyidagicha bo'lsin.

kichik kvadratlar usuli asosida quyidagi sistemani tuzamiz[12]:

$$\begin{cases} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \right) a + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right) b = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i \\ \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right) a + nb = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Tenglamalar sistemasidan a va b noma'lumlarga quyidagicha topamiz:

$$a = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^2}, \quad b = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^2}. \quad (2)$$

Topilgan a va b larga asosan regressiya tenglamasini quyidagicha yozamiz[4]:

$$\tilde{y} = ax + b.$$

Topilgan modelni-chiziqli regressiya tenglamsini statistik baholash.

1.Model sifatini baholash. Model sifatini baholash uchun o'rtacha yaqinlashish:

$$\bar{A} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \tilde{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \cdot 100\%.$$

Bu og'ishlar qanchalik kichik bo'lsa, topilgan qiymatlar nazariy qiymatlarga shunchalik yaqinroq bo'ladi. Bu modelni sifat-samaradorligini bildiradi. O'rtacha xatolikni 8-10% miqdorda bo'lishi, yoki 12-

$$F = \frac{\bar{S}_y^2}{\bar{S}_{gold}^2}$$

bunda $\bar{S}_y^2 = \frac{1}{k_1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i - \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i \right)^2 \right)$ - umumiy dispersiya, $\bar{S}_{gold}^2 = \frac{1}{k_2} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \tilde{y})^2$ - qoldiq

dispersiya. Regressiya tenglamasi tajriba natijalari \bar{y} ortachaga nisbatan necha marta yaxshiroq ekanligin aniqlaydi uni yuqoridagi dispersiyalarning nisbatidan topamiz. Bu F kriteriya qiymati ilova

xatoligi aniqlanadi. U hisoblangan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiy ma'lumotlardan o'rtacha og'ishi (aproksimatsiyasi) ni quyidagi formuladan aniqlaymiz

15% dam oshmasligi modelni sifatli ekanini anqlaidi.

2.Model adekvatligini baholash. Regressiya tenglamasini adekvatligini Fisherning F -kriteriyasi asosida quyidagi formula bilan aniqlaymiz:

jadvalidagi $F_{tab}(\alpha, k_1, k_2)$ qiymat bilan taqqoslanadi, bunda α - qiymatdorlik, $k_1 = n - 1$, $k_2 = n - m - 1$ erkinlik darajalari, n -tajribalar soni, m - x ga tegisli parametrlar soni. Bu holda:

-agar hisoblash natijasi bo'yicha $F > F_{tab}$ bo'lsa, topilgan regressiya tenglamasi adekvat (statistik qiymatdor);

-agar $F < F_{tab}$ bo'lsa, regressiya tenglamasi adekvat emas.

$$t_a = \frac{a}{m_a}, \quad t_b = \frac{b}{m_b},$$

$$m_a = \frac{S_{qold}}{\sigma_x \sqrt{n}}, \quad m_b = \frac{1}{n \sigma_x} S_{qold} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}$$

bunda $\bar{S}_{qold}^2 = \frac{1}{n-2} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \tilde{y})^2$ -qoldiq dispersiya va $\sigma_x = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i\right)^2}$ -o'rtacha

kvadratik og'ishma. Bu t_a, t_b lar $v=n-2$ erkinlik darajasi bo'yicha Styudent taqsimotiga bo'ysunadi. Styudent kriteriyasi uchun tuzilgan taqsimot jadvalidan kritik qiymatni $t_{kr}=t(\alpha, v)$ kabi topamiz:

1) agar $t_a > t_{kr}$ bo'lsa, parametr a statistik qiymatdor, aks holda qiymatdor emas;

2) agar $t_b > t_{kr}$ bo'lsa, parametr b statistik qiymatdor, aks holda qiymatdor emas.

Maple dasturi

a) To'g'ri chiziqi bog'lanishni yuqorida ko'rsatilgan qoida asosida:

> restart; with(stats):

> Digits:=5:

Tajriba natijalari asosida topilgan qiymatlar:

> x1:=1.5:x2:=4:

x3:=5:x4:=7:x5:=8.5:x6:=10:

x7:=11:x8:=12.5:

> y1:=5:y2:=4.5: y3:=7:y4:=6.5:

y5:=9.5:y6:=9: y7:=11:y8:=9:

Tasodifiy miqdorlar:

3. Regressiya koeffitsentlarining qiymatdorligini baholash.

Styudent kriteriyasi bo'yicha, koeffitsentlarning a va b qiymatlarini ularning tasodifiy xatoliklari m_a va m_b bilan taqqoslash asosida baholaymiz:

Endi yuqorida $n=8$ ta kuzatishlar bo'yicha tuzilgan jadval asosida topilgan to'g'ri chiziqi regressiya tenglamasi (model) ning sifatini, adekvatligini, koeffitsentlarining qiymatdorligini aniqlash masalalarining yechimini topishda to'g'ridan-to'g'ri quyida tuzilgan Maple dasturidan foydalanamiz.

>

X:=Vector([x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6,x7,x8],data type=float):

>

Y:=Vector([y1,y2,y3,y4,y5,y6,y7,y8],data type=float):

Tasodifiy miqdorlarni chiziqi bog'lanish koeffitsentlarini va tenglamasini aniqlash:

> n:=8:

> SX:=add(X[i],i=1..n); SX := 59.500

> SY:=add(Y[i],i=1..n); SY := 61.500

> SXX:=add(X[i]^2,i=1..n); SXX := 541.75

> SYY:=add(Y[i]^2,i=1..n); SYY := 509.75

>

SXY:=add(X[i]*Y[i],i=1..n);

SXY := 510.25

To'g'ri chiziqi bog'lanish tenglamasining koeffitsentlarini aniqlash(2):

```
>
ab:=solve({a*SX+n*b=SY,a*SXX+b*SX=SXY},{a,b});
```

$ab := \{a = 0.53260, b = 3.7263\}$

To'g'ri chiziqi bog'lanish tenglamasini aniqlash:

```
> yt:=ab[1]*x+ab[2];
yt := xa + b = 0.53260x + 3.7263
> a:=.532; b:=3.726; a := 0.532
```

$b := 3.726$

To'g'ri chiziqi bog'lanish qiymatlari va yig'indisi:

```
> Yt:={seq(a*X[i]+b,i=1..n)};
Yt := {4.5240, 5.854, 6.386, 7.450, 8.2480, 9.046, 9.578, 10}
> SXY2:=add((Y[i]-a*X[i]-b)^2,i=1..n);
SXY2 := 8.8245
```

To'g'ri chiziqi bog'lanishdan tajriba qiymatlarining o'rtacha og'ishlari va yig'indisi:

```
> A:=seq(abs((Y[i]-a*X[i]-b)/Y[i]),i=1..n); A:=evalf(%,4)*100;
```

1.5000	5.	2.2500	25.	7.5000	4.5250	0.22558	9.4990
4.	4.5000	16.	20.250	18.	5.8563	1.8396	30.140
5.	7.	25.	49.	35.	6.3888	0.37356	8.7310
7.	6.5000	49.	42.250	45.500	7.4538	0.90973	14.670
8.5000	9.5000	72.250	90.250	80.750	8.2526	1.5561	13.130
10.	9.	100.	81.	90.	9.0513	0.0026317	0.57000
11.	11.	121.	121.	121.	9.5838	2.0056	12.870
12.500	9.	156.25	81.	112.50	10.383	1.9114	15.360
59.500	61.500	541.75	509.75	510.25	`-`	8.8242	104.98

Bu o'zgaruvchilarning qiymatlaridan va oxirgi sardagi yig'ndilaridan chiziqli bog'lanishni statistik baholashlarda foydalanamiz:

1) Topilgan bog'lanishning samaradorligi:

```
> At:=add(abs((Y[k]-a*X[k]-b)/Y[k]),k=1..n)/n;
At := 0.13112
```

$A := 9.49900, 30.1400, 8.73100, 14.6700, 13.1300, 0.570000, 12.8700$

```
> SA:=add(abs((Y[i]-a*X[i]-b)/Y[i]),i=1..n)*100;
```

$SA := 104.90$

Quyidagi o'zgaruvchilarga mos qiymatlarini va ularning yig'indilarini aniqlash jadvalini tuzamiz:

```
> print("X[i],Y[i], X[i]^2, Y[i]^2, X[i]*Y[i], Yt=a*X[i]+b, (Y[i]-Yt)^2,A[i]*%");
"X[i], Y[i], X[i]^2, Y[i]^2, X[i]*Y[i], Yt=a*X[i]+b, (Y
```

```
> u:=array(1..9,1..8);
```

```
> for i to n do for j to n do
u[i,1]:=X[i]; u[i,2]:=Y[i]; u[i,3]:=X[i]^2;
u[i,4]:=Y[i]^2; u[i,5]:=X[i]*Y[i];
u[i,6]:=a*X[i]+b; u[i,7]:=(Y[i]-a*X[i]-b)^2; u[i,8]:=A[i];
u[n+1,1]:=SX; u[n+1,2]:=SY;
u[n,6]:=a*X[i]+b; u[n+1,3]:=SXX;
u[n+1,6]:=`-`; u[n+1,5]:=SXY;
u[n+1,4]:=SYY; u[n+1,7]:=SXY2; u[n+1,8]:=SA;
od;od;
> evalf(evalm(u),4);
```

```
> At:=At*100; At := 13.112
```

Regression bog'lanish bilan tajriba natijasida topilgan qiymatlarning o'rtacha og'ishi: 13.12%.

Aproksimatsiya hatoligi 12-15% dan katta bo'lmasa, tuzilgan bog'lanish modeli yaxshi modeduli hisoblanadi va hisoblarni

oldimdan baholash (prognoz qilish) imkonini beradi.

2) Bog'lanishning adikvatligini baholash:
 n -tajribalar soni va k_1, k_2 erkinlik darajalari:

> $n:=8$; $m:=1$:

> $k1:=n-1$; $k2:=n-m-1$; $k1 := 7$. $k2 := 6$.

> $\#T:=\text{Quantile}(\text{StudentT}(n-1), 1-0.05/2)$;

Umumiy dispersiya:

> $S2y:=(\text{SYY}-\text{SY}^2/n)/k1$; $S2y := 5.2814$

Qoldiq dispersiya:

> $S2qol:=\text{add}((Y[k]-a*X[k]-b)^2, k=1..n)/k2$;

$S2qol := 1.4708$

F-Fisher kriteriyasi:

> $F:=S2y/S2qol$; $F := 3.5908$

Fisher jadvaliga asosan

$Ftab(\alpha, k1, k2) = Ftab(0.05, 7, 6) = 4.21$

> $Ftab:=4.21$; $\#F < Ftab$ chiziqli bog'lanish adekvat

3) Regressiya koeffitsentlarining qiymatligini baholash:

Koeffitsentlarning tasodifiy hatoligini topish:

> $\sigma_x := \text{sqrt}(SXX/n - (SX/n)^2)$;

$\sigma_x := 3.5218$

> $ma := S2qol / (\sigma_x * \text{sqrt}(n))$;

$ma := 0.14766$

> $mb := S2qol * \text{sqrt}(SXX) / (n * \sigma_x)$;

$mb := 1.2151$

Topilan regressiya koeffitsentlarini qiymatdorligini ularning tasodifiy hatoligi (1-rasm)

bilan taqqoslashni Student kriteriyasi bo'yicha baholaymiz:

> $a:=.5325984252$; $b:=3.726299213$;

$a := 0.5325984252$ $b := 3.726299213$

> $ta:=a/ma$; $ta := 3.6069$

> $tb:=b/mb$; $tb := 3.0667$

Student kriteriyasi bo'yicha taqsimot jadvali (ilova) dan kritik qiymatni olamiz:

$t_{kr} = t(\alpha, v) = t(0.05, 6) = 2.45$

Bunda $t_a > t_{kr}$, $t_b > t_{kr}$ bo'lishidan a va b koeffitsentlari statistik qiymatdor ekanligini ko'ramiz.:

> $t_{kr}:=2.45$:

> $ta - t_{kr} > 0$; $0 < 1.1569$

> $tb - t_{kr} > 0$; $0 < 0.6167$

Bu chiziqli bog'lanish-modelining grafisini quramiz.

> restart;

> with(stats):with(plots):

> $x1:=1.5$; $x2:=4$; $x3:=5$; $x4:=7$;

$x5:=8.5$; $x6:=10$; $x7:=11$; $x8:=12.5$;

> $y1:=5$; $y2:=4.5$; $y3:=7$; $y4:=6.5$;

$y5:=9.5$; $y6:=9$; $y7:=11$; $y8:=9$;

>

$r2:=\text{rhs}(\text{fit}[\text{leastsquare}[[x,y], y=a*x+b, \{a, b\}]]([x1, x2, x3, x4, x5, x6, x7, x8], [y1, y2, y3, y4, y5, y6, y7, y8]]))$;

$r2 := 0.5325984252x + 3.726299213$

>

$\text{plot}([r2, [[x1, y1], [x2, y2], [x3, y3], [x4, y4], [x5, y5],$

$[x6, y6], [x7, y7], [x8, y8]]], x=1..13, 4..12,$

$\text{style}=[\text{line}, \text{point}],$

$\text{color}=[\text{blue}, \text{red}], \text{thickness}=3,$

$\text{symbol}=\text{BOX}, \text{symbolsize}=30)$;

1-rasm.

XULOSA. Demak, kichik kvadratlar usuli asosida topilgan chiziqli bog'lanish-modeli Fisherning F kriteriyasi bo'yicha to'la adiqvat bo'lib, uning barcha koeffitsentlari qiymatdor ekanligini topdik. Berilgan tajriba natijalari bo'yicha xulosa

va qaror qabul qilish uchun topilgan modelni tuzis va samaradorligini aniqlashda Maple dasturidan foydalanib aniq, tez va sifatli natijalarni olish mumkinligini ko'rdik.

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